

A Content Analysis of Secondary History

Textbooks in Somalia

In the Light of Fostering Historical Thinking Skills

Dr. Said Abubakar Sheikh Ahmed

Dean, Faculty of Arts and Director of Research Unit, Mogadishu
University

Email: baashaa4@gmail.com

Abstract

This article aims to examine the extent of the secondary history textbooks in Somalia, which consist of four grades to foster historical thinking skills. Thus, to achieve the purpose of the study, the researcher followed a deductive method of qualitative content analysis by using the QDA MINER LITE and SPSS. The results revealed that there was a significant difference between the four grades of the secondary history textbooks associated with fostering the historical thinking skills as well as among proportions of the five benchmarks of the historical thinking skills to the four grades. The results of the study also showed that grade 10 has the highest rank of fostering the historical thinking skills while grade 9 represents the lowest rank.

Key Words: Content Analysis, Secondary, History, Thinking Skills, Fostering

1. Introduction

After the collapse of the Somali central government in 1991, the education system in Somalia faced complex and multidimensional challenges in the areas of curriculum, teacher training, school infrastructure, lack of public education, school finance, and untrained educational professionals. The number of imported curricula was used in the schools ranging from 10-24 (Hussein, 2015). From 1991-2011 the role of the government was very limited in provision of educational services. The private education sector was administered by associations called Education Umbrellas in an attempt to fill this gap due to the circumstances surrounded the country. Many efforts were paid by the Ministry of Education, UNESCO, UNICEF, IDB Islamic Development Bank and Education Umbrellas to unify curriculum. In order to unify the curriculum, the Ministry of Education decided in 2009 to conduct secondary certificate examinations where the Education Umbrellas concerned with the possibility of implementation of this exam due to the curriculum differences not only among them but among the schools under the supervision of every Umbrella. In 2011, Educational umbrellas agreed with the memorandum of understanding of the development of education, especially the unification of educational subjects for all grades depending on their own resources which led successfully publishing in 2014 syllabus and textbooks from grade 1-12. This was one of the main events recorded in the history of education in Somalia after the collapse of the Somali central government in 1991 which pushed the MoE to develop the secondary syllabus and textbooks prepared by the Education Umbrellas and held the secondary certificate examination for all the schools in the south

and central regions in Somalia. (Said,2018) https://mu.edu.so/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/V2_Part2A.pdf

One of the main educational problems faced Somali education is a curriculum. The social study subject is the main educational issues which many educators paid a lot efforts to develop it. There was a constant demand from parents to reform this subject and focus on the nation's history and culture. This article aims to analyze the contents of the secondary textbooks in Somalia on the basis of historical thinking skills. The researcher considers, according his knowledge, this article is the first study was conducted in Somalia. Based on the above discussion, the researcher proposes the following hypotheses:

- H_a1. There is a significant difference among the five historical thinking skills included in the content of the secondary history textbook in Somalia for the grade 9 at level 0.05.
- H_a2. There is a significant difference among the five historical thinking skills included in the content of the secondary history textbook in Somalia for the grade 10 at level 0.05.
- H_a3. There is a significant difference among the five historical thinking skills included in the content of the secondary history textbook in Somalia for the grade 11 at level 0.05.
- H_a4. There is a significant difference among the five historical thinking skills included in the content of the secondary history textbook in Somalia for the grade 12 at level 0.05.
- H_a5. There is a significant difference among the four grades of the secondary history textbooks in Somalia in light of historical thinking skills included in the contents at level 0.05.

There are empirical studies that have examined the content analysis for history textbooks in light of historical thinking skills include Content Analysis of Selected Secondary History Textbooks' Portrayals of Christopher Columbus, Hernan Cortes, and Francisco Pizarro(Lillejord, Ed, & Ellis, 2014),The Norwegian curriculum in history and historical thinking: a case study of three lower secondary schools(Johanson, 2017),A Review of Social Studies Textbook Content Analyses Since 2002(Roberts, 2014).

2. Content Analysis

Content analysis is a research technique for making reapplicable and valid inferences from texts (or other meaningful matter) to the contexts of their use(Kim, Nelson, & Williams, 1985).

Content analysis is an approach to quantify qualitative information by systematically sorting and comparing items of information in order to summarize them. (Manual, 2013).Qualitative content analysis has been defined as: “a research method for the subjective interpretation of the content of text data through the systematic classification process of coding and identifying themes or patterns” (Shannon, Zhang, & Wildemuth, 2005).

2.1 Approachesto Content Analysis

Content analysis is a method that may be used with either qualitative or quantitative data; furthermore, it may be used in an inductive or deductive way. Which of these is used is determined by the purpose of the study. If there is not enough former knowledge about the phenomenon or if this knowledge is

fragmented, the inductive approach is recommended (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008)

2.2 The Process of Qualitative Content Analysis

The process of qualitative content analysis can be followed as these steps: preparing the data, defining the unit of analysis, developing categories, coding scheme, testing the coding scheme on a sample of text, coding all the text, assessing coding consistency and finally drawing the conclusions from the coded data (Shannon et al., 2005)

2.3 The Aims of Content Analysis

The aim is to attain a condensed and broad description of the phenomenon, and the outcome of the analysis is concepts or categories describing the phenomenon. Usually, the purpose of those concepts or categories is to build up a model, conceptual system, conceptual map or categories (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008)

2.4 Function of Content Analysis

The main functions of content analysis may be classified as follows:

1. Confirmation and validation of hypotheses which already presumed.
 2. To accurate “optical illusions” which may be shared by most specialists.
 3. To resolve disagreements among specialists as the truth value of certain propositions.
 4. To permit the formulation and the testing of hypotheses.
- (Luis et al., 2008)

2.5 Historical Thinking Skills

Historical thinking refers to exploring evidence and the ability to criticize them; understanding the changes of time; and admitting that history is about the development and destruction of a nation or government. It is also about being emphatic about the past and to dig the reasons for certain events based on cause and effects. (Awang, Ahmad, Yakub, & Seman, 2016).

Historical thinking skills (HTS) is generally defined as a process of using historical information, including deciphering context, perspective, point of view, and perceived facts to understand the past. Thinking in history, or the use of phrases such as “thinking history” also may refer to a process of using critical thinking skills or higher level of thinking skills in the study of history.(Puteh, Maarof, & Tak, 2010).

Seixas, P., & Peck, C. (2004), the historical thinking skills are categorized in five Benchmarks they are historical significance, primary source evidence, continuity and change, cause and consequence, historical perspectives and moral dimension.

2.6 Secondary Education

Secondary education serves as a bridge between elementary and higher education and prepares young persons the age group of 14-18 for entry into higher education (Wells, 1958) likely the secondary education system in Somalia currently is four years for the students aged 14-18. The general objectives and the contents of secondary history subject in Somalia, which consist of four grades and the student should encounter them are shown below.

The General Objectives of the Secondary History in Somalia 2017 (Waxbarashada & Sare, n.d.)

After studying history in a secondary school in Somalia, students are expected to be able to

1. Recognize and appreciate the importance of studying the history of their nation, both ancient and modern, and how the historical affects the lives of people locally and globally.
2. Understand the important aspects of the history of the wider world, the nature of ancient civilizations, the expansion of empires and their collapse, and the distinctive features of the achievements of previous societies.
3. Develop the historical-critical skills of the social, economic and political organizations of African societies.
4. Understand and appreciate the rights, privileges, and obligations of self and others in order to promote a just and peaceful society.
5. Understand historical concepts such as continuity, results, similarities, and differences, use them to conduct relationships, plot contradictions, analyze trends and develop historically correct questions.
6. Understand historical research methods, including how to use evidence strongly to make historical claims, and determine how to adapt past arguments and interpretations

According to the above six objectives of secondary schools in Somalia, there is a match among the historical thinking skills stated in the objectives and the required standards of historical thinking skills to the study. The below table indicates the matrix of the contents of the four secondary history textbooks in Somalia.

Table 1. Contents of the Four Grades for the Secondary History Textbooks in Somalia

Units	Grade 9	Grade 10	Grade 11	Grade 12
1	Introduction to History and Government	Trade	The History of Africa	Ottoman Caliphate
2	Early Man	Development of Transport and Communication	European Invasion of Africa and The Process of Colonization	World Wars
3	Development of Agriculture	Development of Industry	The Rise of African Nationalism	International Relations
4	History of Islam	Urbanization	The Rise and Contribution of Somalia Freedom Fighters	Cooperation in Africa
5	Contacts between East Africa and the Outside World Up to the 19 th Century	Origin, Migration, and Settlement of the People of Somalia	National Defense, Maintain, Law and Order	Women Rights
6	Citizenship and National Integration	Human Rights (Political & Economic Rights)	Human Rights (Social & Cultural Rights)	Caring for the Earth
7	Resolve Conflict Non-Violently	Tolerance	Justice	Optimism
8	-	Respect of Others' Opinion	Public Interest	Contented Living
9	-	Discipline in Physical Behavior	Discipline in Speech	

3. Methodology

This study is a deductive which the researcher begins the analysis, using the pre-existing categories (analysis matrix) imposed by the theory or previous research findings (Armat, Assaroudi, Rad, Sharifi, & Heydari, 2018). It is a method of Qualitative Content Analysis which the author examined the contents of the four secondary history textbooks in Somalia in light of Benchmarks of Historical Thinking, a Framework for Assessment in Canada, Peter Seixas, Centre for the Study of Historical Consciousness, UBC, August 18th, 2006 (Qian & Western, 2007) they are categorized in five Benchmarks they are historical significance, primary source evidence, continuity and change, cause and consequence, historical perspectives and moral dimension. Seixas, P., & Peck, C. (2004) "The historical significance is about a relationship not only among events and people of the past, but also about the relationship of those events and people to us, in the present as well as it involves organizing events in a narrative that will show us something important about our position in the world". The primary source evidence is the use of primary sources as evidence. This includes how to find, select, interpret, and contextualize primary sources. There are distinctions among forms of evidence, e.g., records, testimony, relics, demanding some different kinds of questions (Qian & Western, 2007). As for the continuity and change are interrelated: processes of change are usually, continuous, not isolated into a series of discrete events this include progress, decline and the chronology and periodization of events (Qian & Western, 2007), while the causes and consequences: central to cause and consequence are the active role, or agency, that people (as individuals and groups) play in promoting, shaping, and resisting change in history (Qian & Western, 2007) and the perspective, empathy, and making a moral judgment or dimension, for the perspective is the cognitive act of understanding the different social, cultural,

intellectual, and even emotional contexts that shaped people's lives and actions in the past while the moral judgments mean the actions of people in the past, through the historical context in which they were operating.(Qian & Western, 2007)

The author used abbreviations for the coding the items of the Benchmarks of historical thinking skills for analyzing the contents of the four history textbooks of the study in which HS stands for historical significance, PS coded as primary source evidence, COC represents continuity and change while CAC coded as cause and consequence and HP stands for historical perspectives and moral dimension.The author analyzed sentences, paragraphs, pictures,tables and diagrams included in the contents of the textbooks by using QDA Miner Lite.

To determine the consistency of the instrument, the author selected equal units randomly from the contents of the textbooks and examined them, then after two weeks re-examined and checked inter-rater reliability according to Kappa in SPSS. The result was 0.75 with $p < .00$ (Table 1) thus it is substantial.

Table 2: Inter-rater Reliability

		Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Measure of Agreement	Kappa	.750	.210	3.536	.000
N of Valid Cases		5			

4. Findings and Discussions

Built on the content analysis of the four secondary history textbooks in Somalia examined by the author, though testing the five Hypotheses of the study in light of Benchmarks of Historical Thinking,a Framework for Assessment in Canada,Peter

In the Light of Fostering Historical Thinking Skills

Seixas, Centre for the Study of Historical Consciousness, UBC, August 18th, 2006 (Qian & Western, 2007), the feedback and discussions illustrated below through the various tables.

Table 3. Correspondance Table of the Historical Thinking Skills with the Four History Textbooks

Historical Thinking Skills	Frequency			
	Grade 9	Grade 10	Grade 11	Grade 12
Historical Significance	12	23	20	25
Primary Sources	15	20	38	62
Continuity & Change	21	77	32	53
Cause & Consequence	16	49	28	32
Historical Perspective & Moral Judgments	3	35	29	15
Total	67	204	147	187
Percentage %	11%	34%	24%	31%

The table above shows the total frequency points for each grade of the four secondary history textbooks with their weights in light of fostering historical thinking skills, and so, the grade 10 gained the most frequencies (204) 34%, the grade 12 gained a second rank (187) 31%, while the grade 11 reached the middle rank (147) 24%, however, the grade 9 represents the lowest rank (67) with 11%. The table 4 explores the frequency of each benchmark of historical thinking skills for the grades horizontally with their percentages.

Table 4. Comparing Proportions among Historical Thinking Skills for Each Grade of the History textbooks at Secondary Schools in Somalia.

Historical Thinking Skills	Averages			
	Grade9	Grade10	Grade 11	Grade 12
Historical Significance	18%	11%	13%	14%
Primary Sources	22%	10%	26%	33%
Continuity & Change	31%	38%	22%	28%
Cause & Consequence	24%	24%	19%	17%
Historical Perspective & Moral Judgments	4%	17%	20%	8%

The table above shows the comparison among the four grades in light of historical thinking skills benchmark. For the grade 9, the Continuity&Change, obtained the highest level with 31% and the Historical Perspective Gained lower level, 5%, while the grade 10, the high degree gained by the Continuity& Change 38% and the Primary Sources shows the low level 10%. For grade 11, the Primary Sources reached a high level with 26%, whereas the Historical Significance obtained the low level 13%. According to grade 12, the Primary Sources represent the high level of 33% compared with other historical thinking skills, while the Historical Perspective& the Moral Judgments contributed the low rank 8%. For all grades in general, the Continuity&Change,the Primary Sources and the Cause & Consequence gained a high rank in all grades. The Historical Significance and the Historical Perspective& Moral Judgmentsrevealed the lowest rank.Based on the above discussion, the following chart highlights how the extent of the relationships among the historical thinking skills,

In the Light of Fostering Historical Thinking Skills

and the four grades of textbooks for the study. The chart indicates the row and column points where the row represents historical thinking skills and the column stands for the grades.

The above chart indicates that the continuity & change and cause & consequence are more closed with the grade 10 while, historical significance has a better relationship with the grade 12 and fairly with primary sources, meanwhile, historical prospective and moral judgement somewhat closed with the grade 11 as well as the continuity and change slightly closed with the grade 9.

4.1. Testing Hypotheses

Table. 5. Calculation of Chi-square for Historical Thinking Skills, Grade9

The table illustrates that the calculated χ^2 with 4 degrees of freedom at the 5% level of significance is 13.226 (Table) and the table value is 9.488 hence the calculated value of χ^2 is higher than the table value. This means that there is a significant difference among the historical thinking skills included in the content of the secondary history textbook for grade 9. Thus, the hypothesis two which says '*there is a significant difference among the historical thinking skills included in the content of grade 9*' was supported.

Historical Thinking Skills	O _i	E _i	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	(O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
Historical Significance	12	13.4	1.4	1.96	0.146
Primary Sources	15	13.4	-1.6	2.56	0.19
Continuity & Change	21	13.4	-7.6	57.76	4.31
Cause & Consequence	16	13.4	-2.6	6.76	0.50
Historical Perspective && Moral Judgment	3	13.4	10.4	108.6	8.08
Total	67				13.226

$$\chi^2 = 13.226$$

Table 6. Calculation of Chi-square for Historical Thinking Skills, Grade10

The table shows that the calculated χ^2 with 4 degrees of freedom at $\alpha=.05$ level of significance is 52.02 (Table) and the table value shows 9.488 hence the calculated value of χ^2 is higher

In the Light of Fostering Historical Thinking Skills

than the table value. This indicates that there is a significant difference among the historical thinking skills included in the content of the secondary history textbook for grade 10. Thus, the hypothesis two which says ‘*there is a significant difference among the historical thinking skills included in the content of grade 10*’ was supported.

Historical Thinking Skills	O _i	E _i	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	(O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
Historical Significance	23	40.8	-17.8	289	7
Primary Sources	20	40.8	-20.8	432.6	10.6
Continuity& Change	77	40.8	836.22	1310.4	32
Cause & Consequence	49	40.8	8.2	67.4	1.6
Historical Perspective && Moral Judgments	35	40.8	-5.8	33.6	0.82
Total	204				52.02

$$\chi^2 = 52.02$$

Table7. Calculation of Chi-square for Historical Thinking Skills,Grade11

The table reveals that the calculated χ^2 with 4degrees of freedom at $\alpha=.05$ level of significance is 5.785(Table) and the table value indicates 9.488 hence the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. We can determine that there is not a significant difference among the historical thinking skills included in the content of the secondary history textbook for grade 11, thus, the hypothesis three which says ‘*there is a significant difference among the historical thinking skills included in the content of grade 11*’ was not supported.

Historical Thinking Skills	O _i	E _i	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	(O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
Historical Significance	20	29.4	-9.4	88.36	3
Primary Sources	38	29.4	8.6	73.96	2.5
Continuity& Change	32	29.4	2.6	6.76	0.22
Cause & Consequence	28	29.4	-1.4	1.96	0.06
Historical Perspective && Moral Judgments	29	29.4	-0.4	0.16	0.005
Total	147				5.785

$$\chi^2 = 5.785$$

Table 8. Calculation of Chi-square for Historical Thinking Skills, Grade 12

Table explores that the calculated χ^2 with 4 degrees of freedom at the 5% level of significance is 41 (Table) and the table value showed 9.488 hence the calculated value of χ^2 is higher than the table value. We can thus, conclude that there is a significant difference among the historical thinking skills included in the content of the secondary history textbook for grade 12. Thus, the hypothesis two which says '*there is a significant difference among the historical thinking skills included in the content of grade 12*' was supported.

Historical Thinking Skills	O _i	E _i	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	(O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
Historical Significance	25	37.4	-12.4	153.7	4.1
Primary Sources	62	37.4	24.6	605.2	16.2
Continuity& Change	53	37.4	15.6	243.3	6.5
Cause & Consequence	32	37.4	-5.4	29.2	0.8
Historical Perspective&& Moral Judgments	15	37.4	-22.4	501.7	13.4
Total	187				41

$$\chi^2 = 41$$

Table 9. Calculation of Chi-square of Historical Thinking Skills among the Four Grades

This table shows the calculation of Chi-square results of historical thinking skills among the four grades the significance value in the table = 000 is less than 0.05. We can thus conclude that there is a significant difference among the five historical thinking skills included in the contents of the secondary history textbooks for all grades and therefore, the hypothesis that ‘*there is a significant difference among the four grades in light of fostering historical thinking skills*’ was supported.

Dimension	Singular Value	Inertia	Chi Square	Sig.
1	.246	.061		.000 ^a
2	.145	.021		
3	.058	.003		
Total		.085	51.394	

5. Conclusion

As the comparing among the four grades of the study, the findings showed that the grade 10 gained the most frequencies of historical thinking skills 34% while the grade 12 gained a second level, 31%, however, the grade 9 represents the lowest level with 11%. For a comparison among the five benchmarks of historical thinking skills for each grades the results explored that the Continuity&Change, the Primary Sources and the Cause & Consequence gained a high rank for all grades, whilst the Historical Significance and the Historical Perspective&& Moral Judgments revealed the lowest rank.

6. Limitations & Suggestion for Future Research

The findings in this study concentrated on analyzing the content of secondary history textbooks in light of historical thinking skills, thus, the results could not be generalized to the other criteria of content analysis as well as other stages of education system especially, The primary education. Thus, future researches related to analyzing and evaluation of history textbooks for the primary stage are recommended as well as conducting studies on the extent of the achievement of history teachers regarding to fostering historical thinking skills for the primary and secondary education

References

- Armat, M. R., Assarroudi, A., Rad, M., Sharifi, H., & Heydari, A. (2018). The Qualitative Report Inductive and Deductive: Ambiguous Labels in Qualitative Content Analysis Recommended APA Citation. *The Qualitative Report*, 23(1), 219–221. Retrieved from <https://nsuworks.nova.edu/tqr/vol23/iss1/16>
- Awang, M. M., Ahmad, A. R., Yakub, N. M., & Seman, A. A. (2016). Historical Thinking Skills among Pre-Service Teachers in Indonesia and Malaysia. *Creative Education*, 07(01), 62–76. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2016.71007>
- Elo, S., & Kyngäs, H. (2008). The qualitative content analysis process. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 62(1), 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2007.04569.x>
- Johanson, L. B. (2017). The Norwegian curriculum in history and historical thinking: a case study of three lower secondary schools. *Acta Didactica Norge*, 9(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.5617/adno.1301>
- Kim, S., Nelson, J. G., & Williams, R. S. (1985). Mixed-basis band-structure interpolation scheme applied to the fluorite-structure compounds NiSi₂, AuAl₂, AuGa₂, and AuIn₂. In *Physical Review B* (Vol. 31). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.31.3460>
- Lillejord, J. S., Ed, D., & Ellis, A. K. (2014). *A Content Analysis of Selected Secondary History Textbooks' Portrayals of Christopher Columbus, Hernan Cortes, and Francisco Pizarro*. 1(3), 51–60.
- Luis, J., Raigada, P., Porta, L., Nacional, U., Mar, D., Miriam, M., ... Morse, J. M. (2008). Content Analysis: Objective, Systematic, and Quantitative Description of Content. *International Encyclopedia of Communication*, 3(1), 402–442. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732308314930>
- Manual, P. (2013). *United States Government Accountability Office Participant Manual Content Analysis: Principles and Practices*. (July).
- Puteh, S. N., Maarof, N., & Tak, E. (2010). Students' perception of the teaching of historical thinking skills. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 18(SPEC. ISSUE), 87–95.
- Qian, S., & Western, I. S. (2007). Forum : Chinese and Western Historical Thinking. *History and Theory*, 46(May), 194–200.
- Roberts, S. L. (2014). A Review of Social Studies Textbook Content Analyses Since 2002. *Social Studies Research and Practice*, 9(3), 51–65.

- Seixas, P., & Peck, C. (2004). *Teaching historical thinking*. In A. Sears & I. Wright (Eds.), *Challenges and Prospects for Canadian Social Studies* (pp. 109-117). Vancouver: Pacific Educational Press. (2004). 109–117.
- Shannon, S. E., Zhang, Y., & Wildemuth, B. M. (2005). *Qualitative Analysis of Content by*. 15(9), 1277–1288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732305276687>
- Waxbarashada, W., & Sare, T. (n.d.). *Qaabdhismeedka Manhajka Waxbarashada Qaranka Soomaaliyeed*.
- Wells, P. C. (1958). Secondary Education. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 9(4), 437–438. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002248715800900420>
- Armat, M. R., Assarroudi, A., Rad, M., Sharifi, H., & Heydari, A. (2018). The Qualitative Report Inductive and Deductive: Ambiguous Labels in Qualitative Content Analysis Recommended APA Citation. *The Qualitative Report*, 23(1), 219–221. Retrieved from <https://nsuworks.nova.edu/tqr/vol23/iss1/16>
- Awang, M. M., Ahmad, A. R., Yakub, N. M., & Seman, A. A. (2016). Historical Thinking Skills among Pre-Service Teachers in Indonesia and Malaysia. *Creative Education*, 07(01), 62–76. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2016.71007>
- Elo, S., & Kyngäs, H. (2008). The qualitative content analysis process. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 62(1), 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2007.04569.x>
- Johanson, L. B. (2017). The Norwegian curriculum in history and historical thinking: a case study of three lower secondary schools. *Acta Didactica Norge*, 9(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.5617/adno.1301>
- Kim, S., Nelson, J. G., & Williams, R. S. (1985). Mixed-basis band-structure interpolation scheme applied to the fluorite-structure compounds NiSi₂, AuAl₂, AuGa₂, and AuIn₂. In *Physical Review B* (Vol. 31). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.31.3460>
- Lillejord, J. S., Ed, D., & Ellis, A. K. (2014). *A Content Analysis of Selected Secondary History Textbooks' Portrayals of Christopher Columbus, Hernan Cortes, and Francisco Pizarro*. 1(3), 51–60.
- Luis, J., Raigada, P., Porta, L., Nacional, U., Mar, D., Miriam, M., ... Morse, J. M. (2008). Content Analysis: Objective, Systematic, and Quantitative Description of Content. *International Encyclopedia of Communication*, 3(1), 402–442. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732308314930>
- Manual, P. (2013). *United States Government Accountability Office Participant Manual Content Analysis: Principles and Practices*. (July).

In the Light of Fostering Historical Thinking Skills

- Puteh, S. N., Maarof, N., & Tak, E. (2010). Students' perception of the teaching of historical thinking skills. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 18(SPEC. ISSUE), 87–95.
- Qian, S., & Western, I. S. (2007). Forum : Chinese and Western historical thinking. *History and Theory*, 46(May), 194–200.
- Roberts, S. L. (2014). A Review of Social Studies Textbook Content Analyses Since 2002. *Social Studies Research and Practice*, 9(3), 51–65.
- Seixas, P., & Peck, C. (2004). *Teaching historical thinking*. In A. Sears & I. Wright (Eds.), *Challenges and Prospects for Canadian Social Studies* (pp. 109-117). Vancouver: Pacific Educational Press. (2004). 109–117.
- Shannon, S. E., Zhang, Y., & Wildemuth, B. M. (2005). *Qualitative Analysis of Content by*. 15(9), 1277–1288.
- <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732305276687>
- Waxbarashada, W., & Sare, T. (n.d.). *Qaabdhismeedka Manhajka Waxbarashada Qaranka Soomaaliyeed*.
- Wells, P. C. (1958). Secondary Education. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 9(4), 437–438. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002248715800900420>

